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Leadership Influence of Women on Spiritual Formation of Children

Sunday Adeyemo ADEPOJU, PhD

Grace Community Baptist Church, Apapa, Lagos
revsundayadepoju@gmail.com, +2348063235577

Abstract

Women's involvement in leadership positions is controversial, especially in some African religious organisations. Some Christians confined women's activities to mere listening and obeying instructions rather than allowing them to provide leadership inputs. On the other hand, some give them ample opportunity to lead. Thus, this study examines the influence of women's leadership on children's spiritual formation. The paper established the rationales for spiritual formation of children from various views and posits that women's roles in the spiritual formation of children cannot be underestimated. The research adopts a descriptive design; relevant information was gathered through secondary sources, and findings were reported qualitatively. The findings revealed that women have many ways of influencing children to build them up spiritually. Therefore, Christians and churches in Africa should provide a leadership template for women to influence children and nurture them spiritually.

Keywords: Leadership, Women, Spiritual Formation, Children, Churches

Introduction

Over the years, women's involvement in leadership roles in religious and non-religious organisations has been debated. Divergent opinions emerged on whether women should hold leadership positions, especially in church

settings. While it is a welcome idea in some climes, it breeds scepticism and contempt in others. However, leadership, as described by many leadership experts, carries the idea of influencing a group of people to achieve common goals (Adedokun, 2018). It is worth noting that the ability to influence people does not exclusively reside in the male gender; both males and females have the propensity to influence people. And so, women can provide leadership just like their male counterparts.

It must be noted from the outset that women have always been directly or indirectly involved in leadership positions in the church settings. Their positive influence on people, especially children, is a testament to this claim. Therefore, this paper examined women's leadership influence on children's spiritual formation within the purview of the Baptist denomination in Nigeria, also known as the Nigerian Baptist Convention.

Nature of Spiritual Formation in Children

Spiritual formation is an elusive concept that cannot be narrowed down to a single definition. While some people conceived it as a process of growth in a confined and isolated monastic area, others considered it as growth that occurs in a relationship with God and man (Taylor, 2001, 92). Taylor enunciates that spiritual formation is deeper than merely transferring knowledge from teacher to learner. It is a process concerned with an individual's complete growth and development. This implies that spiritual formation is much more than a structured school or church programme. It is a relationship between an individual and God, through the assistance of a more mature person(s).

As defined by Robert Clark (1994, 234), spiritual formation in children "is a step by step and stage by stage process through which a child is guided, encouraged, nurtured, admonished and disciplined to develop as a Christian through the work and the power of the Holy Spirit." In other words, it is a systematic approach by which children are being guided to grow in God's knowledge and become responsible. Ishola-Esan (2016, 185) enunciates that spiritual formation is the purposeful process of forming and integrating the marks of authentic Christian spirituality. In effect, genuine Christian growth and development are measured by the transformation that takes place in an individual's life.

While alluding to the statement of Paul, the Apostle in Romans 12:2, Galatians 4:19 and Ephesians 3:16-21, Ishola-Esan (2016, 187) remarks

that spiritual formation carries the idea that involves a process of “transformation; conforming and formation.” All of these work together until Christ’s image is formed in believers’ lives. In essence, spiritual formation aims to become like Christ and conform to his image. Concerning transformation, Ishola-Esan maintains that it is yielding oneself to the leading of the Holy Spirit by deliberate and intentional decision to suppress the natural propensities of the flesh to grow into Christ-likeness. In essence, transformation in spiritual formation is a continuous process of walking step by step with Christ through the instrumentality of the Holy Spirit until the image of Christ is formed in us.

Regarding conforming, Ishola-Esan (2016) avows that to become like Christ is to grow in His knowledge. Hence, spiritual formation is a process of conforming to the image of Christ through our knowledge of Him. William also offers a complementary position, as cited by Woodard, that “...taking on the character of Christ is a process of discipleship to Him under the direction of the Holy Spirit and the word of God” (2019). So, conforming to the image of Christ is also an ongoing process.

Reflecting on formation, Ishola-Esan (2016, 188) analyses that the principle of spiritual formation is “systematic, continuous, perpetual, interactive and developmental.” The systematic aspect explains the methodical and orderly manner in which spiritual formation is carried out, especially in children. It is also an ongoing process through the collaborative efforts of the teachers and learners. The three ideas involved in spiritual formation, “transformation, conforming and formation,” as enunciated by Ishola-Esan, are ongoing processes of becoming like Christ. The process cuts across every stage of human growth and development.

Developmental psychologists also noted that learning takes place in children in stages. For instance, Piaget’s popular four stages of children’s development from the cognitive (mental) perspective, as cited by Ayo-Obiremi (2014), which are sensory motor (birth- about 2 years); pre-occupational thought (2-7years); concrete operations (7-10/11 years), and formal operations (11/12 years have their peculiarities and approaches which should be taken into consideration in the process of spiritual formation of children. In view of the foregoing, Ayo-Obiremi (2014) counsels that adults or teachers involved in the spiritual formation of children need to be well-grounded in the word of God and doctrinal beliefs to help bring about the expected transformation.

Rationales for Spiritual Formation of Children

It is essential to be aware of the motivations for the spiritual formation of children and why it should be a priority. Child developmental Psychologists, in their discourse, provide insights into the needs for the spiritual formation of children. They postulated theories and developed principles that make spiritual formation of children a necessity. This section, examines few theories in relation to spiritual formation of children, as discussed below.

Faith development theory, postulated by James Fowler, reveals the rationale for spiritual formation of children. Fowler maintains that “every human being is born with a spiritual inclination towards a Supreme Being/God” (Fowler, 2001, 162). This suggests that the need for spiritual growth is not limited to adults; children also have spiritual needs that must be attended to. In light of this assertion, Ola (2019) enunciates that the foundation of a child’s spiritual growth is developed from what Fowler referred to as the primal stage. It is a stage where a child’s “seed of faith” is planted, and the foundation of their growth in God is laid.

Erikson’s psychosocial theory of personality development also explains children’s need for spiritual formation. Erikson elucidates that children go through the emotional stages of trust and mistrust. So, the kind of care they receive can impact their emotional and spiritual growth, either positively or otherwise (Yount, 1996). By implication, what children become in the future can be traced to their spiritual foundation. Hence, the need for spiritual formation of children.

In addition to the above, Lawrence Kohlberg’s theory of Moral development also espoused the need for spiritual formation of children because every stage of moral development requires some level of assistance to help them fit into society. It helps a child build acceptable societal behaviour (Stonehouse, 1998). It is, therefore, important to note that a child’s spiritual life directly connects with a child’s moral behaviours. This helps explain the rationale for spiritual formation of children. Other rationales for spiritual formation of children are highlighted below:

1. ***Children are Made in God’s Image:*** As the image of God (Genesis 1:27), human beings are both physical and spiritual beings that need physical growth and spiritual nurture. The process of nurturing human’s spiritual being is what is referred to as spiritual formation. So, both young and old need spiritual formation. Commenting on the

need for spiritual formation of children, Barret (2004) and Hinde (2010) present similar perspectives that human minds, respond religiously in the ways they think, relate with one another and act. In view of this, children, like any other human beings, need to be connected with God, and this can be possible through the process of spiritual formation.

2. ***Children are Precious in the Sight of God:*** The Bible affirms that children are the heritage of the Lord (Psalm 127:3). This implies that they are precious and should be well taken care of to become well-formed physically, spiritually, intellectually, and socially. Jesus demonstrates how precious children are and the importance of their spiritual formation when He cautioned His disciples not to hinder them from coming to Him. “Let the little children come to me, and do not to hinder them, for the kingdom of heaven belongs to such as these” (Matthew 19:14 NIV). While reinforcing the need for spiritual formation of children, Kiarie (2016), citing Stonehouse, argues, that Jesus takes the child’s faith and protection seriously by given special attention to their spiritual formation and development. Mbiti (1969) also opines that “children are blessing from God and a source of new life and hope for continuity in the community.” These remarks further enunciate the need for spiritual formation of children.
3. ***Biblical Directives:*** It becomes imperative to train children, especially in their spiritual formation, because God commanded it. Deuteronomy 6:4-9 gave an express command to parents to teach and nurture children. Also, Proverbs 22:6 states, “Train up a child the way he should go, and when he is old, he will not depart from it” (NKJV). Commenting on the above Bible passage, Choun (1998) asserts that to train a child the way he should go implies, given them a sense of direction in life. This means that if a child is well nurtured in the way of the Lord, he will become who God intends him to be and fulfil God’s purpose in life.
4. ***It is a Way to Prepare them for the Future:*** Spiritual formation of children is necessary because it helps prepare them for the future. A common axiom has been, “Children are leaders of tomorrow” It is worthy of note that a well-nurtured child will become a responsible individual in the future. In tandem with this maxim, Areo (2018, 92) asserts that “children must be taught to love God and his word. They

must be taught about Jesus and his plans for their lives. Children need to know how to respond to God in faith and worship and learn about the church and the world.”. Also, Miller (2015) stresses the importance of spiritual formation of children, that because they are spiritual beings, they require spiritual nurture to become responsible Christians, prepared to live up to Christian standards and faith as they grow.

5. ***As an Antidote to the Negative Influence of Peers:*** Children are not exempted from the influence of peer pressure. Mangal (2007), in line with other child developmental psychologists, argues that peer group plays a significant role in the life of children. They learn a lot by interacting with their mates in the society, school, and even church. Suffice it to note that peer influence is not always positive; the negative side of it can have adverse effects on children’s behaviours if they are not properly guided. Commenting on the negative influence of peer pressure, Ayandokun (2013) laments that children are exposed to external peer pressure due to technological advancement and modernisation, leading them to be susceptible to negative influence. Therefore, Spiritual formation is necessary to serve as a remedy to the negative influence of peer groups.
6. ***To Withstand Societal Ills:*** Human society has been bedevilled with differing issues of corruption and moral decadence through the influence of social media. Also, the effects of postmodernism are eating hard on this generation. It is now a matter of responsibility that all stakeholders should rise to the challenge by effectively performing their roles in the spiritual formation of children (Quinn, 1999). Similarly, Shirer (2011) notes that, like any other individual, children normally lean to the direction of their fleshly propensities; they are prone to learning negative influences from social media and indulge in rebellious acts. One way to guard against this menace or to ameliorate it is to expose children to spiritual formation process so that they can withstand any temptation that may come their way.

Biblical Basis for Women Involvement in Spiritual Formation of Children.

The involvement of women in the spiritual formation of children is biblically rooted. The Bible makes it crystal clear that parents are responsible for teaching and training their children in the way of the Lord (Proverbs 22:6).

In her observation, Ishola (2016) asserts that this training is meant to establish the child on the foundation upon which their life would be based. Essentially, this training would help children to fulfil God's purpose for their existence.

A cursory look into the Bible, both Old and New Testaments, reveals that women have always been pillars to reckon with when it comes to the spiritual formation of children. It is worth noting that the family has been the primary institution saddled with the responsibility of teaching children. The *Shema* in Deuteronomy 6:4-9 is an injunction for parents to teach their children the law of the Lord. Lawson (2001) referred to this as the daily activities of parents that must not be toiled with. Corroborating this stance, Ayandokun (2013) remarks that "the task of teaching, nurturing, caring are (sic) all directly the responsibility of the family." In effect, the family is essentially saddled with the task of spiritual formation of the children.

Slaughter (1988) observes that family plays a crucial role in the history of Israel with respect to children's education. He explains further that Hebrew children learn about God and His divine provision through family instructions and annual observation of Passover. From the foregoing, it must be stressed that women play a supportive role alongside men in the spiritual training of children

When the lives of Israelites' male children were in danger in Egypt by the cruel directives of Pharaoh to execute them, as recorded in Exodus 2:1-10, Jochebed, Moses' mother, cared for him. Moses was not only well nurtured physically; he was also raised spiritually. This is reflected in his refusal to be called the child of Pharaoh's daughter (Hebrews 11:24). In a similar vein, it was on record that Hannah pledged to give God back her son if and when she is blessed with a son. She fulfilled her promise by bringing Samuel to the temple for dedication (1samuel 1:24-28). Samuel was well-formed spiritually as he grew and found favour with God and man. When there was a record of scarce revelation in the land of Israel in Samuel's time, His spiritual "antennae" were so active that he could hear the Lord (1Samuel 3:1-12). This perhaps culminated in his call into the priesthood and prophetic ministries.

The New Testament also has records of women who were involved in the spiritual development of Children. Worthy of note is Mary, the mother of Jesus. Mary nurtured Jesus and was well brought up that it was testified of him that he matured physically, intellectually, socially, and spiritually

(Luke 2:52). As a woman who was involved in the spiritual growth and development of her child, several mysteries about Jesus were revealed to Mary that she treasured in her mind and pondered about them (Luke 2:19). In addition, Timothy's spiritual growth and fervency were not unconnected to the spiritual nurture received from Eunice and Lois, his mother and grandmother, respectively. Paul, the apostle, in his remarks, acknowledged the efforts of these women on Timothy thus, "When I call to remembrance the genuine faith that is in you, which dwelt in your grandmother Lois and your mother Eunice and I am persuaded is in you also" (2Timothy 1:5). From the foregoing, the impact of women on the spiritual development of children is biblically based and should not be undermined.

Overview of Women's Involvement in the Spiritual Formation of Children within Baptist Denomination in Nigeria

Baptist women, also known as Women's Missionary Union (WMU), play a significant role in the spiritual formation of children. WMU is a missionary organisation an auxiliary arm of the Nigerian Baptist Convention. Their roles in nurturing and caring for children, especially their spiritual well-being, cannot be underestimated. Lateju (2019, 383) remarks that even though the church, from the primitive belief, perceived women as figures only to be "seen and not heard." However, the available records reveal that women have been playing remarkable leadership roles in the mission endeavours, especially in the area of spiritual nurture of children. Their involvement in the spiritual nurture and care of children has brought many positive changes in their lives; thus, help expand the kingdom of God on earth.

The story of the WMU is predicated upon a vision to evangelise women and children. The records reveal that a vibrant woman by name Mrs Adeotan Agbebi conceived the idea of forming Baptist Women's League in 1915 (Akinola, 2011). The vision, however, awaited the appointed time and came to birth on 14th March, 1919 at the sixth annual meeting of the Nigerian Baptist Convention that took place at Oke'lerin Baptist Church Ogbomosho, a town in the then Western region (now in Oyo State) of Nigeria (Lateju, 2019). It was documented that the first official gathering of women took place under a tree after the approval was granted by the Convention leadership. Chief among their vision statement was the concern for children's spiritual, moral, mental, and physical development (Lateju,

2019). In their bid to translate this vision into a mission, four (4) sub-organisations were founded, namely: Sunbeam Band; Girl's Auxiliary (G.A.); Lydia Auxiliary; and Women's Missionary Society (WMS) (Lateju, 2019). Of these four organisations, the first two, Sunbeam Band and Girl's Auxiliary, fall within the categories of children, which is the focus of this paper. Their age-graded are 4-9 years and 10-16 years, respectively (History of WMU of Nigerian Baptist Convention, 2020).

To actualise the purpose of these age-graded groups, specialised programmes were developed to nurture them spiritually to become mature in the knowledge of the Lord and be useful in kingdom business expansion. Lateju (2019) enunciates that WMU engaged children (Sunbeam and Girl's Auxiliary) in spiritual formation through organisation of specially designed programmes such as mission study, annual week of prayer, forward steps (a structured discipleship programme for G.A), stewardship of giving and influence, evangelism, community service and a host of other programmes. Some of these programmes are done annually, some weekly, while some are carried out as projects during school vacations, which take the children to mission fields both within and outside Nigeria. These programmes allow the children to pray and intercede for missionaries and other people worldwide. It also helps them develop stewardship of giving as they are taught to cheerfully give money, clothes, and other materials towards missions and to mission fields. They also develop interest in witnessing through evangelistic rallies and tracts sharing within and outside their church community. They are also encouraged to win at least one soul for Christ in a year, do follow up and report.

Additionally, through these various programmes, children are taught to keep the word of God in their hearts through Bible memory drills. They are also encouraged to learn Bible verses by heart. The Sunbeam band and G.A. are encouraged to participate in community service, giving them a sense of belonging in the community. They visit motherless babies' homes and hospitals. They are also guided to help the aged do some domestic chores, present gifts, and offer prayers for them. (Lateju, 2019). It must be noted that these mission involvements of both the Sunbeam Band and G.A. is geared towards the spiritual formation of the children in different categories.

Leadership Roles of Women on Children's Spiritual Formation

Ministering to spiritual needs of children requires some steps, guidelines, and principles in order to achieve the desired result of spiritual development. Educational Psychologists and childhood educationists are common in their views on the roles that adults, especially women, can play to educate and guide children in life. These steps and guiding principles form the basis upon which this section is built.

1. **Teaching:** One major pillar of the Great Commission is teaching. Everyone, especially children, needs to be taught to keenly observe all that our Lord and Saviour Jesus Christ commanded us (Matthew 28:19-20). So, as explained earlier, women, as seen from their family and conventional roles, are to teach children the word of God. Children are tender and receptive to learning in their formative years. The report of a study carried out by ACK Diocese of Thika on women's roles in teaching children, documented by Kiarie (2016, 3), shows that "more than eighty per cent of Sunday school teachers are women." This report is not far from what is obtainable in the Baptist denomination in Nigeria. Therefore, Mogute (2018) encouraged women to take advantage of their formative years to teach them to be committed and obedient to God so as to live to serve God and humanity. She explains further that children well taught in their formative years manifest virtues earlier inculcated by mothers (women) in childhood and apply them in adulthood.
2. **Encouraging:** Children's spiritual life grows in an atmosphere of warmth and care. Women have a variety of ways to encourage them to learn and grow in the knowledge of God. Several programmes being organised by women such as camping, holiday Bible school, retreat, Bible quiz competitions, and a host of others are programmes with incentives attached to encourage the children to participate actively and are part of women's leadership roles on spiritual formation of children.
3. **Modelling:** Women also help in spiritual formation of children through role modelling. It must be noted that women influence children and the influence reflects in their lives later in life. This view is established from Fowler's faith development theory, as cited by Kiarie, that "children's spiritual development and formation is highly influenced and shaped by those close to children" (2016, 6). The

influence of women on children at this stage of their growth is so strong that children watch and learn from them, and they emulate what they do and say. This position is also reinforced by the social learning theory postulated by Bandura. The theory observes that children learn by observing and imitating what they see people say and do (Bandura, 1971). This is seen from the influence of Lois and Eunice on Timothy. Role modelling, as mentioned earlier, helped to shape Timothy's faith. Alluding to the necessity of role modelling, Pullman (2001, 66) recommends that role models who can offer mentoring support could help a great deal, so women are in a good position to do this. Emphasising this, Taylor (2001, 94), while citing Fowler, maintained that role models are "mirrors" from which children can reflect. Women can serve in this capacity.

4. **Motivating:** Children are human beings who have wills and emotions. They need motivation to do well and to perform to the best of their ability. Emphasising this, Mogute (2018, 43) posits the need for motivating children thus: "The motivation for children to develop spiritually partly comes from the observations children make about their parents (or any other ones) passion and love for God." So, motivation is an essential that women play to help develop spiritual life of children.
5. **Discipling:** It is also important to note that discipleship plays a vital role in the lives of children. It is a spiritual discipline that helps children and adults to be firmly established in the Lord. Ishola (2016) referred to this type of training as a continuous process in the life of an individual for growth. In other words, discipleship would help in children's spiritual formation as it will empower them to integrate virtues and fear of God in their daily lives.
6. **Ministry of Presence:** It is common knowledge that women spend more time with children than men. Even though the influence of technology has reduced this trend, the impact of women on children in terms of availability is still notable. Kiarie (2016) underscores the importance of women's presence in the lives of children by asserting that women's presence is an expression of love, care, and concern for their challenges. He explains further that the mutual relationships between women and children at home and churches serves as an avenue to strengthen the bond of relationship that helps in

developing their spiritual life. Astley (1991) also stresses the importance of women's presence in the life of Children. He argues that the influence of parents, especially women, on the spiritual life of children is essential. He maintains that women are closer to children by nature. Hence, their influence through the ministry of presence, demonstration of warmth, and love helps a great deal in spiritual development of children.

Conclusion

This paper has examined women's leadership influence on children's spiritual formation. It is argued that since leadership is influence, the role of leadership is not limited to male gender; women also lead by influencing people, especially children. The paper maintained that just like any other individual, children need spiritual nurture, and women are at the centre stage of influencing them through spiritual formation. An overview of WMU of the Nigerian Baptist Convention reveals practical ways in which women influence children's spiritual formation.

The work established that the leadership influence of women cannot be undermined in the spiritual formation of children. So, various ways women can influence children to nurture them spiritually were presented. Therefore, Christians and churches in Africa should provide a leadership template for women to influence children and nurture them spiritually. This would help them grow in the knowledge of God and help to confirm into Christ likeness which would culminate in having a better society.

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